

Taxonomical investigation on Braconidae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonoidea) fauna in northern Cyprus, with twenty six new records for the country

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ABSTRACT. In order to determine Braconidae fauna of Cyprus, adult specimens of Braconidae were collected from different habitats of Northern Cyprus between 2012 and 2016. All specimens were collected in both natural vegetation and agricultural areas using sweeping-net. A total of 42 species belonging to 14 genera of Agathidae, Braconinae, Cheloninae, Doryctinae, Euphorinae, Homolobinae, Opiinae and Rogadinae were reported from the Northern Cyprus, of which 26 species are recorded from Cyprus for the first time.

Key words: Pentadaktylos, Braconidae, fauna, Cyprus, parasitoid.

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Introduction

Braconidae is a large family of Hymenoptera, consisting of 1032 genera and approximately 17,963 known species. Thirty seven of 47 subfamilies of the Braconidae are recorded from the west Palaearctic region (Yu et al., 2012). The vast majority of the species are ectoparasitoids mainly among coleopterous and lepidopterous hosts, although a few attack Diptera, Hymenoptera-Symphyta and possibly Hemiptera (Wang et al., 2010).

Cyprus is divided into four geological zones: (a) the Pentadaktylos (Kyrenia) Zone; (b) the Troodos Zone or Troodos Ophiolite; (c) the Mamonia Zone or Complex, and (d) the Zone of autochthonous sedimentary

rocks (Fig. 1). The Pentadaktylos (Kyrenia) Zone, the northern-most geological zone of Cyprus, is considered to be the southern-most portion of the Tauro-Diranide Alpine Orogenic Zone. The base of the Zone is mostly composed of a series of allochthonous massive and recrystallized limestones, dolomites and marbles of Permian-Carboniferous to Lower Cretaceous age (between 350–135 Ma). These are stratigraphically followed by younger autochthonous sedimentary rocks of Upper Cretaceous to Middle Miocene age (67–15 Ma), on which the older allochthonous formations have been thrust southward (Anonymous, 2004).

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Figure 1. Four geological zones of Cyprus (Anonymous, 2004)

The area of this research covers the Pentadaktylos (Kyrenia) Zone and partially the Troodos Zone or Troodos Ophiolite. Cyprus is located in the eastern Mediterranean basin, and is the third largest (9 251 km²) Mediterranean island after Sicily (25 710 km²) and Sardinia (24 090 km²). Cyprus is 70 km from Turkey (Syria 110 km, Egypt 418 km, and Greece 965 km). The Braconidae fauna of Cyprus consists of 124 species. It is similar with 65% (81 species) of Turkey, 64% (79 species) of Greece, 14.4% (18 species) of Egypt and 9.6% (12 species) of Syria (Yu et al., 2012).

The Braconidae fauna of Cyprus has been partially investigated. In Cyprus, there are known 124 species of Braconidae according to *Terrestrial Arthropods of Cyprus* (Anonymous, 2015). The first study of the Braconidae fauna of Cyprus was conducted by Papp (1990) and he worked the fauna of Greece and however, he also identified the Braconids of south Cyprus. We conducted a study on Braconidae fauna in northern Cyprus between 2012 and 2016. A total of 42 species belonging to 14 genera of Agathidinae, Braconinae, Cheloninae,

Doryctinae, Euphorinae, Homolobinae, Opiinae and Rogadinae were reported from Northern Cyprus. Twenty-six species are recorded from Cyprus for the first time.

Material and methods

Adult specimens of Braconidae were collected from different habitats of northern Cyprus by sweeping-nets between 2012 and 2016. Publications consulted for distributional data include: Fischer (1999), Nixon (1986), Papp (1982, 1990, 1998, 1999), Shenefelt (1978), Tobias (1986), and Yu et al. (2012). The following literature was used for taxonomic examination of the material: Matthews (1970), Shaw & Huddleston (1991), Fischer (1999), Achterberg (2003), Marsh & Shaw (2003), Fischer & Beyarslan (2011, 2012, 2013), Beyarslan et al. (2013) and Beyarslan (2014, 2015b).

Information on parasitoids, hosts and general distributions (in terms of zoogeographical region), and parasitoids of the determined species are given according to Yu et al. (2012). The subgenera and species are listed alphabetically. Known

host plants are given in square brackets (Yu et al., 2012). All specimens are deposited in the collection of the Department of Zoology, Bitlis Eren University, Bitlis, Turkey. An asterisk (*) is used within the text for the species that are recorded as new from Cyprus.

Results

Subfamily: Agathidinae

Genus: *Agathis* Latreille, 1804

**Agathis malvacearum* Latreille, 1805

Material examined: Northern Cyprus-İnönü, wild herb, 09.04.2015, 1♀; İskele, barley, 07.04.2015, 3♂♂.

Hosts: **DIPTERA, Tachinidae:** *Actia nudibasis* Stein, 1924; **LEPIDOPTERA, Coleophoridae:** *Coleophora galbulipennella* Zeller, 1838 [*Silene* sp.]; *C. graminicolella* Heinemann, 1876; **Gelechiidae:** *Metzneria aestivella* (Zeller, 1839); *M. lappella* (Linnaeus, 1758) [*Arctium minus*]; *Pexicopia malvella* (Hübner, 1805); **Pterophoridae:** *Hellinsia didactylites* (Ström, 1783).

Distribution: Holarctic, Cyprus (new record).

Subfamily: Braconinae

Genus: *Bracon* Fabricius, 1804

Subgenus: *Bracon* 1804 s.str.

**Bracon (Bracon) gusaricus* Telenga, 1933

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - İskele, barley, 07.04.2015, 4♀♀, 1♂.

Hosts: Unknown.

Distribution: Palaearctic, Cyprus (new record).

Bracon (Bracon) intercessor Nees, 1834

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Beşparmak dağları, Taşocağı, wild herb, 08.04.2015, 1♂; Bostancı, wheat, 27.03.2012, 2♀♀; Dıpkarpaz, Büyük Kumsal, barley, 07.04.2015, 1♂; Girne, Çatalköy, wild herb, 08.04.2015, 1♂; Göçeri wild herb, 30.05.2012, 1♀; İnönü, barley, 09.04.2015,

1♂; İskele, wild herb, 28.03.2012, 2♂♂; Köprülü, wild herb, 01.06.2012, 2♂♂; Mehmetcik, wild herb, 31.05.2016, 1♂; Şirinevler, barley, 30.05.2012; 1♂; Taşpınar, wheat, 31.05.2012, 2♂♂; Türkmenköy, barley, 01.07.2012, 2♀♀; Yeşilırmak, barley, 01.6.2016, 2♀♀, 2♂♂.

Hosts: **COLEOPTERA, Apionidae:** *Oxystoma opeticum* Bach, 1854; **Attelabidae:** *Attelabus nitens* (Scopoli, 1763); **Cerambycidae:** *Agapanthia villosoviridescens* (De Geer, 1775); *A. violacea* (Fabricius, 1775); *Anthonomus (Anthonomus) pedicularius* (Linnaeus, 1758); *A. pomorum* Linnaeus 1758; *A. (A.) sorbi* Germar, 1821; *Hytoecia coerulescens* (Scopoli, 1763) [*Anchusasp.*]; *Curculio salicivorus* (Paykull, 1792); *C. crux* (Fabricius, 1776); *Lixus brevirostris* Boheman, 1835; *L. incanescens* Boheman, 1835 [*Atriplex patula hastata*]; *L. (Compsolixus) juncii* Boheman, 1835; *Microlarinus lareynii* (Jacquelin du Val, 1852); *M. lypriformis* (Wollaston, 1861); *Sibinia (Sibinia) femoralis* Germar, 1824; **Rhynchitidae:** *Rhynchites bacchus* (Linnaeus, 1758); **DIPTERA, Agromyzidae:** *Liriomyza huidobrensis* (Blanchard, 1926); **HYMENOPTERA, Eurytomidae:** *Tetramesa hyalipennis* (Walker, 1832); *Tetramesa rossica* (Rimsky-Korsakov, 1914); **Tenthredinidae:** *Pontania bella* (Zaddach, 1876); *P. kriechebaumeri* Konow, 1901 [*Salix nigricans*]; *P. pedunculi* (Hartig, 1837); *P. vesicator* (Bremi-Wolf, 1849); *P. viminalis* (Linnaeus, 1758); *P. (Eupontania) acutifoliae* Zinovjev, 1985; **LEPIDOPTERA, Coleophoridae:** *Coleophora atraphaxidellum* Kuznetsov, 1957; **Elachistidae:** *Parametriotes theae* Kuznetsov, 1916; **Gelechiidae:** *Scrobipalpa obsoletella* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1841); **Sesiidae:** *Bembecia hungarica* (Tomala, 1910); *Chamaesphecia astatifformis* (Herrich-Schaffer, 1846); *Paranthrene tabaniformis* (Rottemburg, 1775); *Synanthedon culiciformis* (Linnaeus, 1758); **Tortricidae:** *Sparganothis pilleriana* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775); **Yponomeutidae:** *Argyresthia conjugella* Zeller, 1839.

Distribution: Palaearctic, Cyprus (Papp 1998).

***Bracon (Bracon) pectoralis* (Wesmael, 1838)**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Akdeniz, wheat, 01.06.2016, 2♀♀; Beşparmak dağları, Taşocağı, barley, 08.04.2015, 1♂; Mehmetcik, wild herb, 30.05.2016, 1♀; Serdarlı, wild herb, 30.05.2016, 4♀♀; Yeşil köy, barley, 30.05.2016, 3♀♀, 5♂♂.

Hosts: COLEOPTERA, Curculionidae: *Larinus flavescens* Germar, 1824; DIPTERA, Tephritidae: *Xyphosia miliari* (Schrank, 1781); HYMENOPTERA, Cynipidae: *Aphelonyx cerricola* (Girayd, 1859); LEPIDOPTERA, Alucitidae: *Alucita hexadactyla* (Linnaeus, 1758); *A. huebneri* Wallengren, 1859; Gelechiidae: *Sitotroga cerealella* (Olivier, 1789); Pyralidae: *Etiella zinckenella* (Treitschke, 1832); Tortricidae: *Aethes francillana* (Fabricius, 1794).

Parasitoids: HYMENOPTERA, Torymidae: *Exopristus trigonomerus* (Masi, 1916). Ichneumonidae: *Scambus elegans* (Woldstedt, 1877).

Distribution: Palaearctic, Cyprus (Papp 1990, 1998).

***Bracon (Bracon) luteator* Spinola, 1808**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Akdeniz, wild herb, 01.05.2016, 1♂; Dipkarpaz, barley, 31.05.2016, 2♀♀ 4♂♂; Serdarlı, wild herb, 30.30.05.2016, 1♀, 1♂; Taşpınar, wheat, 31.05.2012, 2♀♀; Türkmenköy Karpaz, barley, 01.07.2012, 1♀; wild herb, 31.05.2016, 1♂; Yeşilirmak, wild herb, 01.05.2016, 1♀, 1♂; Yeşilköy, barley, 30.5.2016, 1♀.

Hosts: DIPTERA, Tephritidae: *Urophora solstitialis* (Linnaeus, 1758); LEPIDOPTERA, Gelechiidae: *Metzneria aestivella* (Zeller, 1839); *Metzneria kerzhneri* Piskunov, 1979.

Distribution: Palaearctic, Cyprus (Papp, 1998).

**Subgenus: *CyanopteroBracon* Tobias, 1957
Bracon (CyanopteroBracon) armeniacus Telenga, 1936**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Akdeniz, wild herb, 01.06.2016, 1♀.

Hosts: Unknown.

Distribution: Western Palaearctic, Cyprus (Papp, 1998).

**Subgenus: *GlabroBracon* Fahringer, 1927
Bracon (GlabroBracon) ahngeri* Telenga, 1936

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Girne çatal köy, barley, 8.4.2015, 1♀.

Hosts: Unknown.

Distribution: Oriental, Palaearctic, Cyprus (new record).

***Bracon (GlabroBracon) atrator* Nees, 1834**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Ercan havaalanı, wheat, 8.4.2015, 1♀; Serhatköy, Güzelyurt kavşağı, barley, 09.04.2015, 1♀.

Hosts: COLEOPTERA, Brentidae: *Apion buddenbergi* Bedel (1885); *Gymnetron antirrhini* (Paykull, 1800); *G. campanulae* Schoenherr, 1825; *G. villosulum* Gyllenhal, 1838 [*Veronica* sp.]; DIPTERA, Agromyzidae: *Amauromyza flavifrons* Meigen, 1830; Tephritidae: *Tephritis conura* Loew, 1844; *T. neesii* Meigen, 1830, *T. separata* Rondani, 1871; LEPIDOPTERA, Coleophoridae: *Coleophora coronillae* Zeller, 1849.

Distribution: Palaearctic, Cyprus (Papp, 1998).

***Bracon (GlabroBracon) delibator* Haliday, 1833**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Lefkoşa, Dikkaya, wild herb, 09.04.2015, 1♀.

Hosts: COLEOPTERA, Curculionidae: *Gymnetron campanulae* Schoenherr, 1825; *Hylobius piceus* (De Geer, 1775); Phalacridae: *Olibrus aeneus* Fabricius, 1792 [*Tripleurospermum perforatum*]; DIPTERA, Tephritidae: *Urophora cuspidata* Meigen, 1826; LEPIDOPTERA, Tortricidae: *Cydia strobilella* (Linnaeus, 1758).

Distribution: Palaearctic, Cyprus (Papp, 1998).

****Bracon (GlabroBracon) lividus* Telenga, 1936**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Akdeniz, wild herb, 01.06.2016, 1♀; Türkmenköy, wild herb, 01.07.2012, 5♀♀.

Hosts: HYMENOPTERA, Tenthredinidae: *Pontania vesicator* (Bremer, 1849).

Distribution: Palaearctic, Cyprus (new record).

****Bracon (Glabrobracon) otiosus* Marshall, 1885 (syn. *macrurus*)**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Yeşilirmak, wild herb, 01.06.2016, 2♂♂; Yeşilköy, wild herb, 30.05.2016, 1♂.

Hosts: COLEOPTERA, Curculionidae: *Anthonomus pomorum* (Linnaeus, 1758); *Magdalis rufa* Porta, 1932; **HYMENOPTERA, Tenthredinidae:** *Nematus (Bacconematus) pumilio* (Konow, 1903); **LEPIDOPTERA, Agonoxenidae:** *Blastodacna atra* (Haworth, 1828).

Distribution: Palaearctic, Cyprus (new record).

****Bracon (Glabrobracon) parvulus* (Wesmael, 1838)**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Türkmenköy, wild herb, 01.07.2012, 1♀.

Hosts: DIPTERA, Agromyzidae: *Amauromyza flavifrons* Meigen, 1830; **Cecidomyiidae:** *Clinodiplosis strobili* Kieffer, 1909; **Tephritidae:** *Chaetostomella cylindrica* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830 [*Chrysanthemum* sp.]; *Tephritis bardanae* Schrank, 1803; *T. conura* Loew, 1844 [*Cirsium oleraceum*]; *T. pulchra* Loew, 1844 [*Chrysanthemum leucanthemum*, *Scorzonera jaquiniana*]; *Trupanea stellata* (Fuessly, 1775).

Distribution: Oriental and Palaearctic, Cyprus (new record).

***Bracon (Glabrobracon) popovi* Telenga, 1936**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Mehmetcik, barley, 30.06.2016, 1♀.

Hosts: Unknown.

Distribution: Palaearctic, Cyprus (Papp, 1998).

***Bracon (Glabrobracon) variator* Nees, 1811**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Türkmenköy, wheat, 01.07.2012, 4♂♂;

Yeşilirmak, barley, 01.06.2016, 1♀.

Hosts: COLEOPTERA, Anobiidae: *Ernobius nigrinus* (Sturm, 1837); **Buprestidae:** *Coraebus florentinus* (Herbst, 1801); **Chrysomelidae:** *Bruchidius lividimanus* (Gyllenhal, 1833); *B. poupillieri* Allard, 1868; *Bruchus atomarius* (Linnaeus, 1761); *B. laticollis* Boheman, 1833; *B. lentis* Frölich, 1799; *B. viciae* Olivier, 1795; **Curculionidae:** *Anthonomus pomorum* (Linnaeus, 1758); *Baris chlorizans* Germar, 1837; *B. cuprirostris* Germar, 1817; *B. laticollis* (Marsham, 1802); *Ceutorhynchus assimilis* Paykull, 1792; *C. punctiger* (Gyllenhal, 1837); *Gymnetron asellus* (Gravenhorst, 1807); *G. campanulae* Schoenherr, 1825 [*Campanula* sp.]; *G. tetrum* (Fabricius, 1792); *Larinus flavescens* Germar, 1824; *L. jaceae* (Fabricius, 1775); *L. planus* Germar, 1824; *L. turbinatus* (Gyllenhal, 1836); *Magdalis rufa* Germar, 1824; *Pissodes validirostris* Gyllenhal, 1835; *Sibinia viscaria* Linnaeus, 1761; *S. viscaria* Linnaeus, 1761; *Sitona longulus* Gyllenhal, 1834; **DIPTERA, Anthomyiidae:** *Anthomyia albimana* Zetterstedt, 1845; *Botanophila seneciella* Meade, 1892; **Cecidomyiidae:** *Mikiola fagi* (Hartig, 1839); **Tephritidae:** *Sphenella marginata* Fallen, 1814; *Chaetostomella cylindrica* (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830); *Noeta pupillata* Fallen, 1814; *Tephritis leontodontis* (DeGeer, 1776); *Urophora (Carduus) nutans* Fabricius, 1775); **HYMENOPTERA, Tenthredinidae:** *Hoplocampa minuta* (Christ, 1791); *H. brevis* (Klug, 1816); *H. flava* (Linnaeus, 1761); *Caliroa cerasi* (Linnaeus, 1758); **LEPIDOPTERA, Amphipyridae:** *Gortyna xanthenes* Germar, 1844 [*Cynara scolymus*]; **Carposinidae:** *Carposina niponensis* Walsingham, 1900; **Coleophoridae:** *Coleophora coronillae* Zeller, 1849; *C. medelichensis* Krone, 1908; **Gelechiidae:** *Mesophleps corsicella* Herrich-Schäffer, 1856; *Pexicopia malvella* (Huebner, 1805); *Platyedra subcinerea* (Haworth, 1828); **Geometridae:** *Perizoma lugdunaria* Herrich-Schäffer, 1855; **Gracillariidae:** *Phyllonorycter mespillella*

(Huebner, 1805); **Hadeninae:** *Hadena bicruris* (Hufnagel, 1766); **Lycaenidae:** *Lampides boeticus* (Linnaeus, 1767); **Noctuidae:** *Myelois circumvoluta* (Fourcroy, 1785) (*Onopordum acanthium*); **Nymphalidae:** *Vanessa cardui* Linnaeus, 1758; **Pyralidae:** *Etiella zinckenella* (Treitschke, 1832); *Myelois circumvoluta* (Fourcroy, 1785); *Dioryctria abietella* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775); **Sesiidae:** *Synanthedon andrenaeformis* Laspeyres, 1801; **Tortricidae:** *Acleris variegana* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) [*Malus* sp.]; *Barbara herrichiana* Obraztsov 1960; *Cydia dorsana* Fabricius, 1775; *C. funebrana* (Treitschke, 1835); *Eucosma cana* (Haworth, 1811); *Gypsonoma aceriana* (Duponchel, 1843); *Pandemis cerasana* (Huebner, 1786); *Rhopobota naevana* (Malus) (Huebner, 1817); *Rhyacionia resinella* (Linnaeus, 1758). **Distribution:** Palaearctic, Cyprus (Papp, 1990, 1998).

Subgenus: Orthobracon Fahringer, 1927

***Bracon (Orthobracon) longigenis Tobias, 1957**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - İskele, wild herb, 07.04.2015, 1♀.

Hosts: Unknown.

Distribution: Western Palaearctic, Cyprus (new record).

Subgenus: Pigeria van Achterberg, 1985

Bracon (Pigeria) piger (Wesmael, 1838)

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Mehmetcik, barey, 30.06.2016, 1♀, 2♂♂; Girne, Çatalköy, wild herb, 08.04.2015, wheat, 3♂♂; Mağosa, Nergizli, wild herb, 09.04.2015, 1♀; Devlet Üretme çitliği, wheat, 09.04.2015, 1♂.

Hosts: COLEOPTERA, Curculionidae: *Pissodes validirostris* (Sahlberg, 1834); LEPIDOPTERA, Noctuidae: *Heliothis peltigera* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775); Pyralidae: *Etiella zinckenella* (Treitschke, 1832); Tortricidae: *Cnephasia longana*

(Haworth, 1811); *Cydia nigricana* (Fabricius, 1794).

Distribution: Holarctic, Cyprus (Papp, 1998).

Subgenus: Rostrobracon Tobias, 1957

Bracon (Rostrobracon) urinator (Fabricius, 1798)

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Akdeniz, barley, 01.06.2016, 4♀♀; Dipkarpaz, barley, 31.05.2016, 5♀♀; Göçeri wild herb, 30.05.2012, 1♀; Köprüköy, wild herb, 30.05.2016, 1♂; Serdarlı, barey, 30.05.2016, 1♀; Taşpınar, wheat, 31.05.2012, 2♀♀; Türkmenköy, barley, 01.07.2012, (4♀♀; Yeşilirmak, wild herb, 01.06.2016, 1♀.

Hosts: COLEOPTERA, Curculionidae: *Larinus flavescens* Germar, 1824; *L. saussureae* Marshall, 1924; *L. sibiricus* Gyllenhal, 1835 [*Xeranthemum annuum*]; *L. sturnus* (Schaller, 1783) [*Cirsium heterophyllum*]; *L. vulpes* (Olivier, 1807) [*Echinops ritro*]; *Lixus obesus* Petri, 1904 [*Prangos uloptera*]; *Rhinocyllus conicus* (Frölich, 1792) [*Carduus nutans*]; *R. latirostris* Schoenherr, 1826 [*Carduus nutans*]; DIPTERA, Lonchaeidae: *Protearomyia nigra* (Meigen, 1826); Tephritidae: *Tephritis pulchra* Loew, 1844 [*Scorzonera hispanica*].

Distribution: Afrotropical, Oriental and Palaearctic, Cyprus (Papp, 1990, 1998).

Genus: Habrobracon Ashmead, 1895

***Habrobracon concolorans (Marshall, 1900) (syn. nigricans)**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Akıncılar, wild herb, 09.04.2015, 2♀♀; Beşparmak dağı, Taşocağı, wheat, 08.04.2015, 1♀, 3♂♂; Devlet Üretme çitliği, wild herb, 09.04.2015, 1♂; Ercan Havaalanı, wild herb, 09.04.2015, 2♀♀; 1♂; Girne, Çatalköy, wheat, 08.04.2014, 1♀; Girne, Tepebaşı, wild herb, 09.04.2015, 1♂; İnönü, wild herb, 09.04.2015, 1♀, 1♂; İskele, wild herb, 08.04.2015, 3♂♂; Lefkoşa, Dilekkaya, wild herb, 09.04.2015, 7♂♂; Mağosa, Nergizli, wheat, 09.04.2015, 5♂♂; Türkmenköy, wheat, 09.04.2015, 2♂♂.

Hosts: Leiodoptera: Gelechiidae: *Pexicopia malvella* (Huebner, 1805); **Pyralidae:** *Etiella zinckenella* (Treitschke, 1832); **Crambidae:** *Loxostege sticticalis* (Linnaeus, 1761).

Tortricidae: *Cnephasia sedana* Constant 1884.

Distribution: Oriental, Palaearctic, Cyprus (new record).

***Habrobracon stabilis* (Wesmael, 1838)**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Ercan Hava Alanı, wheat, 09.04.2015, 2♀♀, 5♂♂; Gazimağusa, İnönü, wild herb, 09.04.2015, 4♀♀, 11♂♂; Gazimağusa, Nergizli, barley, 09.04.2015, 9♀♀, 2♂♂; Gazimağusa, Türkmen köy, wild herb, 09.04.2015, 9♀♀, 2♂♂; Girne, Başpınar (Beşparmak Taşocağı, 2), barley, 08.04.2015, 5♀♀; Girne, Tepebaşı, wheat, 09.04.2015, 1♀, 1♂; İskele, wheat, 07.04.2015, 2♀♀, 8♂♂; Lefkoşa, Dilekkaya, wheat, 09.04.2015, 2♀♀, 4♂♂; Lefkoşe, Akıncılar, weeds, 09.04.2015, 1♀; Lefkoşe, Çömlekçi (Devlet üretim çiftliği), barley, 09.04.2015, 4♀♀, 3♂♂.

Hosts: COLEOPTERA, Anobiidae: *Ernobius kiesewetteri* Schilsky, 1898; *E. nigrinus* (Sturm, 1837); **Curculionidae:** *Anthonomus pomorum* (Linnaeus, 1758); *Hylesinus crenatus* (Fabricius, 1787); *H. fraxini* (Panzer, 1779); *H. oleiperda* Fabricius, 1792; **Dermestidae:** *Attagenus pello* (Linnaeus, 1758). **Scolytidae:** *Ips typographus* (Linnaeus, 1758); **DIPTERA, Tephritidae:** *Chaetostomella cylindrica* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830; *Noeeta pupillata* (Fallen, 1814); **LEPIDOPTERA, Agonoxenidae:** *Scrobipalpa brahmiella* Heyden, 1862; **Coleophoridae:** *Coleophora laricella* (Huebner, 1817); **Gelechiidae:** *Anarsia spartiella* (Schrank, 1802) [*Ulex minor*]; *Caryocolum marmorea* Haworth, 1829; *Exoteleia dodecella* (Linnaeus, 1758); *Gelechia senticetella* (Staudinger, 1859); *Mirificarma mulinella* (Zeller, 1839); **Lymantriidae:** *Euproctis chrysorrhoea* (Linnaeus, 1758) [*Quercus pubescens*]; **Oecophoridae:** *Agonopterix subpropinquella* (Stainton, 1849); **Pyralidae:**

Ephestia terebellum Zeller, ?; **Tortricidae:** *Archips rosana* (Linnaeus, 1758); *Avaria hyperana* Milliére, 1857; *Choristoneura murinana* (Huebner, 1799); *Clepsis rogana* Guenée, 1845 [*Veratrum album*]; *Cnephasia asseclana* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775); *C. chrysantheana* (Duponchel, 1843); *C. longana* (Haworth, 1811); *Cydia strobilella* (Linnaeus, 1758) [*Abies excelsa*]; *Epinotia nigricana* (Herrich-Schaffer, 1851); *Rhyacionia buoliana* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775); *R. pinivora* (Lienig & Zeller, 1846); *Tortrix viridana* Linnaeus, 1758; *Zeiraphera griseana* (Hübner, 1799); **Yponomeutidae:** *Yponomeuta malinella* Zeller, 1838.

Distribution: Holarctic, Oriental Cyprus (Papp, 1998).

Genus: *Glyptomorpha* Holmgren, 1868

****Glyptomorpha (Glyptomorpha) pectoralis* (Brullé, 1832)**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Akıncılar, wild herb, 09.04.2015, 1♀, 1♂; Beşparmak, Taşocağı, wheat, 08.04.2015, 5♀♀, 1♂; Ercan Hava alanı, wild herb, 09.04.2015, 4♀♀, 6♂♂; Girne, Çatalköy, wheat, 08.04.2014, 1♀, 1♂; Girne, Tepebaşı, wheat, 09.04.2015, 1♀, 2♂♂; İskele, wild herb, 07.04.2015, 2♀♀, 12♂♂; Lefkoşa, Devlet Üretim Çiftliği, wheat, 09.04.2015, 3♀♀, 2♂♂; Lefkoşa, Devlet Üretim Çiftliği, wheat, 09.04.2015, 1♀; Lefkoşa, Dikkaya, wild herb, 08.04.2015, 2♀♀, 6♂♂; Magosa, İnönü, barley, 09.04.2015, 4♀♀, 7♂♂; Magosa, Nergizli, wild herb, 09.04.2015, 1♀, 3♂♂; Serhatköy, Güzelyurt kavşağı, barley, 09.04.2015, 1♂; Türkmenköy, wild herb, 09.04.2015, 9♀♀, 2♂♂.

Hosts: COLEOPTERA, Buprestidae: *Chrysobothris affinis* (Fabricius, 1794); *Sphenoptera gossypii* Kerremans, 1892; *S. laticollis* (Olivier, 1790) [*Onobrychis viciifolia*]; *S. montana* Dejean, 1833; **Cerambycidae:** *Plagionotus arcuatus* (Linnaeus, 1758).

Distribution: Afrotropical, Oriental and Palaearctic, Cyprus (New record).

Genus: *Iphiaulax* Förster, 1862

****Iphiaulax fastidiator* (Fabricius, 1781)**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Mehmetcik, wild herb, 30.06.2016, 1♀, 2♂♂.

Hosts: COLEOPTERA, Curculionidae: *Saperda populnea* (Linnaeus, 1758).

Distribution: Afrotropical and Western Palearctic, Cyprus (New record).

****Iphiaulax jacobsoni* Shestakov, 1927**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Taşpınar wheat, 31.5.2012, 1♀, 2♂♂.

Hosts: Unknown.

Distribution: Eastern Palearctic, Oriental, Western Palearctic: Cyprus (New record).

Genus: *Pseudovipio* Szépligeti, 1896

***Pseudovipio castrator* (Fabricius, 1798)**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Türkmenköy, Karpaz, wild herb, 31.05.2016, 1♀.

Hosts: COLEOPTERA, Buprestidae: *Chrysobothris affinis* (Fabricius, 1794);

Cerambycidae: *Plagionotus arcuatus* (Linné, 1758); **Curculionidae:** *Lixus juncii* Boheman, 1835; **LEPIDOPTERA, Amphipyrrinae:** *Gortyna xanthenes* Germar, 1844 [*Cynara scolymus*].

Distribution: Afrotropical, Palearctic, Cyprus (Papp, 1998).

***Pseudovipio inceptor* (Nees, 1834)**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Türkmenköy, Karpaz, wild herb, 31.05.2016, 1♀.

Hosts: LEPIDOPTERA, Crambidae: *Ostrinia nubilalis* (Hübner, 1796).

Distribution: Palearctic, Cyprus (Papp, 1998).

Subfamily: Cheloninae

Genus: *Chelonus* Panzer, 1806

Subgenus: *Chelonus* Panzer, 1806

****Chelonus (Chelonus) mirandus* Tobias, 1964**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Geçitköy, wild herb, 01.06.2016, 2♂♂.

Hosts: Unknown.

Distribution: Palearctic, Cyprus (New record).

****Chelonus (Chelonus) oculator* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Akıncılar, wild herb, 09.04.2015, 1♀, 1♂; Devlet Üretim Çitliği, barley, 09.04.2015, 3♂♂; Dilekkaya, wild herb, 09.04.2015, 1♀, Girne, Çatalköy, wheat, 09.04.2015, 1♀; 1♂; İnönü, wild herb, 09.04.2015, 1♀; İskele, wild herb, 07.04.2015, 1♀; Lefkoşa, Dikkaya, barley, 09.04.2015, 1♀; Serhatköy, wild herb, 09.04.2015, 1♀.

Hosts: LEPIDOPTERA, Coleophoridae: *Coleophora anatipennella* (Hübner, 1796);

Crambidae: *Loxostege sticticalis* (Linnaeus, 1761); *Ostrinia nubilalis* (Hübner, 1796);

Noctuidae: *Agrotis segetum* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775); *Helicoverpa armigera*

(Hübner, 1805); *Heliothis peltigera* Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775; *H. viroplaca* (Hufnagel,

1766); *Leucania loreyi* (Duponchel, 1827); *Longalatedes elymi* (Treitschke, 1825) (syn.:

Chortodes elymi); *Spodoptera exigua* (Hübner, 1808); *S. littoralis* Boisduval, 1833;

Pyralidae: *Ephestia kuehniella* Zeller, 1879; *Etiella zinckenella* (Treitschke, 1832);

Homoeosoma nebulella Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775; **Tortricidae:** *Cydia corticana* Hübner

(?), *Zeiraphera isertana* (Fabricius, 1794).

Distribution: Western Palearctic, Cyprus (New record).

Subgenus: *Microchelonus* Szépligeti, 1908

****Chelonus (Microchelonus) phalloniae* (Telenga, 1941)**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Serdarlı, wild herb, 30.05.2016, 1♂.

Host: Unknown.

Distribution: Eastern Palaearctic, Cyprus (New record).

Subgenus: *Stylochelonus* Hellén, 1958

**Chelonus (Stylochelonus) pusillus* Szépligeti, 1908

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Mehmetcik, wild herb, 31.05.2016, 1♀.

Host: LEPIDOPTERA, Elachistidae: *Elachista* sp.

Distribution: Palaearctic, Cyprus (New record).

Subfamily: Doryctinae

Genus: *Rhaconotus* Ruthe, 1854

**Rhaconotus (Rhaconotus) testaceus* (Szépligeti, 1908)

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Ercan, Balıkesir, wild herb, 30.05.2016, 1♀.

Hosts: LEPIDOPTERA, Crambidae: *Chilo suppressalis* (Walker, 1863); *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker, 1863).

Distribution: Oriental, Palaearctic, Cyprus (New record).

Subfamily: Euphorinae

Genus: *Meteorus* Haliday, 1835

Meteorus rubens (Nees, 1811)

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Ercan, Balıkesir, wild herb, 30.05.2016, 1♀, 2♂♂; İskele, barley, 07.04.2015, 1♀; Köprüküy, wild herb, 30.05.2016, 1♂; Magosa, İnönü, wild herb, 08.04.2015, 1♀.

Hosts: DIPTERA, Chloropidae: *Meromyza americana* (Fitch, 1856) [*Triticum aestivum*];

LEPIDOPTERA, Coleophoridae: *Coleophora malivorella* (Riley, 1878);

Gelechiidae: *Pexicopia malvella* (Common, 1958);

Phthorimaea operculella; (Zeller, 1873);

Geometridae: *Idaea muricata*; (Hufnagel, 1767);

Lasiocampidae: *Eriogaster lanestris* (Linnaeus, 1758);

Lymantriidae: *Orgyia antiqua* (Linnaeus, 1758);

Noctuidae: *Agrotis exclamationis* (Linnaeus, 1758); *A. gladiaria* (Morrison, 1875); *A. ipsilon* (Hufnagel, 1766);

A. malefida (Guenée, 1852); *A. obesa* (Boisduval, 1829); *A. orthogonia* (Morrison, 1876); *A. segetum* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775); *A. subterranea* (Fabricius, 1794); *A. tokionis* (Butler, 1881); *A. vestigialis* (Hufnagel, 1766); *Anticarsia gemmatalis* (Hübner, 1818); *Apamea devastator* (Brace, 1819); *A. lateritia* (Hufnagel, 1766); *A. zeta* (Treitschke, 1825); *Autographa californica*; (Speyer, 1875); *A. gamma* (Linnaeus, 1758); *Autoplusia egea* (Guenée, 1852); *Celaena leucostigma* (Hübner, 1808); *Cerapteryx graminis* (Linnaeus, 1758); *Discestra trifolii* (Hufnagel, 1766); *Euxoa auxiliaris* (Grote, 1873); *E. messoria* (Harris, 1841); *E. ochrogaster* (Guenée, 1852); *E. perexcellens* (Grote, 1875); *E. temera* (Hübner, 1808); *E. tristicula* (Morrison, 1875); *E. tritici* (Linnaeus, 1761); *Feltia jaculifera* (Guenée, 1852); *F. subgothica* (Haworth, 1809); *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hübner, 1809); *Lacanobia oleracea* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Lithophane antennata* (Walker, 1858); *Mamestra brassicae* (Linnaeus, 1758); *Mesapamea stipata* (Morrison, 1875); *Noctua pronuba* (Linnaeus, 1758); *Ochropleura fennica* (Tauscher, 1806) (Syn. *Actebia fennica*); *Peridroma saucia* (Hübner, 1808); *Spodoptera exigua* (Hübner, 1808); *S. exigua* (Hübner, 1808); *S. frugiperda* (J.E. Smith, 1797); *S. littoralis* (Boisduval, 1833); *S. praefica* (Grote, 1875); *Syngrapha epigaea* (Grote, 1874); *Xestia c-nigrum* (Linnaeus, 1758); **Nymphalidae:** *Vanessa cardui* (Linnaeus, 1758); **Pieridae:** *Achyra bifidialis* (Fabricius, 1794); *Colias eurytheme* (Boisduval, 1852); *Hellula undalis* (Fabricius, 1794); *Nomophila noctuella* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775); *Omphalocera cariosa* (Lederer, 1863); *Pococera militella* (Zeller, 1848); **Thaumetopoeidae:** *Thaumetopoea wilkinsoni* (Tams, 1926); **Tortricidae:** *Acleris maccana* (Treitschke, 1835); *Eupoecilia ambiguella* (Hübner, 1796); *Lobesia botrana* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775); *Pandemis heparana* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775); *Tortrix viridana* (Linnaeus, 1758); **Yponomeutidae:** *Yponomeuta malinella* (Zeller, 1838).

Distribution: Holarctic, Neotropical, Oriental, Cyprus (Papp, 1990, 1998).

****Meteorus versicolor* (Wesmael, 1835)**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Yeşilirmak, barley, 01.06.2016, 1♀.

Hosts: LEPIDOPTERA, Arctiidae: *Hyphantria cunea* (Drury, 1773); *Ocnogyna baetica* (Rambur, 1836); **Argyresthiidae:** *Argyresthia bonnetella* (Linnaeus, 1758); **Geometridae:** *Abraxas pantaria* (Linnaeus, 1767); *Archiearis parthenias sajana* (Prout, 1912); *Ematurga atomaria* (Linnaeus, 1758); *Ennomos erosaria* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775); *Eulithis testata* (Linnaeus, 1761); *Eupithecia exigua* (Hübner, 1813); *Geometra papilionaria* (Linnaeus, 1758); *Operophtera brumata* (Linnaeus, 1758); *Protoarmia porcelaria* (Guenée, 1857); *Tephрина arenacearia* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775); *Thera juniperata* (Linnaeus, 1758); **Lasiocampidae:** *Dendrolimus pini* Linnaeus 1758; *D. spectabilis* (Butler 1877); *Eriogaster lanestris* (Linnaeus, 1758); *E. philippi* Bartel 1911 (*Quercus ithaburensis*); *Lasiocampa quercussicula* (Staudinger, 1861); *Macrothylacia rubi* Linnaeus, 1758; *Malacosoma castrense* (Linnaeus, 1758); *M. neustria* (Linnaeus, 1758); *M. parallelum* Staudinger 1887; *Bombyx lobulina* Denis & Schiffermüller 1775; **Lycaenidae:** *Callophrys rubi* (Linnaeus, 1758); **Lymantriidae:** *Arctornis l-nigrum* (Müller, 1764); *Calliteara pudibunda* (Linnaeus, 1758); *Euproctis chrysorrhoea* (Linnaeus, 1758); *E. flava* Bremen, 1861; *Leucoma salicis* (Linnaeus, 1758) [*Populus grandidentata*, *P. tremuloides*]; *Lymantria dispar* (Linnaeus, 1758); *L. monacha* (Linnaeus, 1758); *Orgyia antiqua* (Linnaeus, 1758); *O. leucostigma* (Smith, 1797); *O. (Clethrogyna) recens* (Hubner, 1819); *O. thyellina* Butler [1979]; *Parocneria detrita* Esper, 1785; *Teia antiquioides* Hubner 1822; **Noctuidae:** *Agrotis exclamationis* (Linnaeus, 1758); *A. segetum* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775); *Anarta myrtilli* (Linnaeus, 1761); *Autographa gamma* (Linnaeus, 1758); *Brachionycha sphinx* (Hufnagel, 1766; *Cosmia*

trapezina (Linnaeus, 1758); *Diachrysia chrysitis* (Linnaeus, 1758); *Noctua porphyrea* Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775; *N. pronuba* (Linnaeus, 1758); *Nycteola asiatica* (Krulikovsky, 1904); *Orthosia carnipennis* Butler, 1878; *O. miniosa* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775); *Panolis flammea* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775); *Xestia agathina* (Duponchel, 1827); *Nola cucullatella* (Linnaeus, 1758); **Notodontidae:** *Clostera anastomosis* (Linnaeus, 1758); **Nymphalidae:** *Maniola jurtina* Linnaeus, 1758; **Pieridae:** *Pieris rapae* (Linnaeus, 1758); **Pyralidae:** *Ercta orientalis* Yamanaka, 1972 [*Ipomoea paniculata*]; *Eurrhynpara hortulata* (Linnaeus, 1758); **Thaumetopoeidae:** *Thaumetopoea pityocampa* Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775 [*Pinus halepensis*]; *T. processionea* (Linnaeus, 1758); *T. wilkinsoni* Tams, 1924 [*Pinus halepensis*]; **Tortricidae:** *Archips oporana* (Linnaeus, 1758); *Pammene inquilina* Fletcher, 1938; *Pandemis cerasana* (Hübner, 1786).

Distribution: Holarctic, Oriental, Cyprus (New record).

Subfamily: Homolobinae

Genus: *Homolobus* Förster, 1862

Subgenus: *Apatia* Enderlein, 1920

***Homolobus (Apatia) truncator* (Say, 1829)**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Ercan Hava alanı, Deneme, wild herb, 09.04.2015, 1♀; Ercan, Balıkesir, barley, 30.05.2016, 1♀; 09.04.2015, 2♀♀; Lefkoşa, Hamitköy, wheat, wild herb, 28.03.2012, 2♀♀; Lefkoşa, Devlet üretme çitliği, wheat, 09.04.2015, 1♀.

Hosts: LEPIDOPTERA, Gelechiidae: *Phthorimaea operculella* (Zeller, 1873); **Geometridae:** *Agriopsis bajaria* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775); *Anisodes lyciscaria* (Guenée, 1858); *Ascotis selenaria* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775); *Besma quercivoraria* (Guenée, 1857); *Casilda consecraria* (Rambur, 1858); *Chiasmia clathrata* (Linnaeus, 1758); *Glossotrophia annae* (Mentzer, 1990); *G. asellaria* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1847); *G.*

(Graslin, 1863); *Hypagyrtis piniata* (Packard, 1870); *Lambdina feroiaria* (Hübner, 1827); *Lambdina fiscellaria* (Guenée, 1857); *Lycia hirtaria* (Clerck, 1759); *L. zonaria* (Dennis & Schiffermüller, 1775); *Pachycnemia hippocastanaria* (Hübner, 1799); *Rhodometra sacraria* (Linnaeus, 1767); **Lasiocampidae:** *Malacosoma neustria* (Linnaeus, 1758); **Noctuidae:** *Agrotis ipsilon* (Hufnagel, 1766); *A. orthogonia* (Morrison, 1876); *A. segetum* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775); *A. subterranea* (Fabricius, 1794); *A. venerabilis* (Walker, 1857); *Anumeta cestina* (Staudinger, 1884); *Autographa gamma* (Linnaeus, 1758); *Calophasia platyptera* (Esper, 1788); *Catocala nymphagoga* (Esper, 1787); *Emmelia trabealis* (Scopoli, 1763); *E. tristicula* (Morrison, 1875); *Helicoverpa zea* (Boddie, 1850); *H. zea* (Boddie, 1850) [*Medicago sativa*]; *Lacanobia contigua* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775); *Mocis latipes* (Guenée, 1852); *M. latipes* (*Cynodon dactylon*) (Guenée, 1852); *Panolis flammea* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775); *Protorthodes smithii* (Dyar, 1904); *Pseudaletia unipuncta* (Haworth, 1809) [*Medicago sativa*]; *Rhyacia simulans* (Hufnagel, 1766); *Spodoptera exigua* (Hübner, 1808) [*Asparagus setaceus*, *Medicago sativa*]; *S. frugiperda* (J.E. Smith, 1797) [*Medicago sativa*, *Sorghum bicolor*]; *S. litura* (Fabricius, 1775); *S. ornithogalli* (Guenée, 1852); *S. ornithogalli* (Guenée, 1852) [*Medicago sativa*]; *Xestia c-nigrum* (Linnaeus, 1758); *X. smithii* (Snellen, 1896); **Pyralidae:** *Achyra rantalis* (Guenée, 1854); *Loxostege sticticalis* (Linnaeus, 1761).

Distribution: Afrotropical, Holarctic, Neotropical, Oriental, Cyprus (Papp, 1998).

Subgenus: *Phylacter* Reinhard, 1863

**Homolobus (Phylacter) annulicornis* (Nees, 1834)

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Magosa, İnönü, wild herb, 09.04.2015, 1♂.

Hosts: LEPIDOPTERA, **Noctuidae:** *Autographa gamma* (Linnaeus, 1758); *Cosmia diffinis* Linnaeus, 1767 [*Ulmus carpinifolia*];

C. trapezina (Linnaeus, 1758); *Dichonia convergens* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775); *Dryobotodes eremita* (Fabricius, 1775); *Fissipunctia ypsilon* Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775; *Lithophane lamda* (Fabricius, 1787); *Mamestra brassicae* (Linnaeus, 1758); *Orthosia populeti* Fabricius, 1775; *Panolis flammea* Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775; *Xestia triangulum* (Hufnagel, 1766).

Distribution: Oriental, Western Palaearctic, Cyprus (**New record**).

Subfamily: Opiinae

Genus: *Biosteres* Förster, 1862

**Biosteres (Chilotrachia) arenarius* (Stelfox, 1959)

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Girne Çatalköy, barley, 8.4.2015, 1♀.

Hosts: Unknown.

Distribution: Palaearctic, Cyprus (**New record**).

Genus: *Opius* Wesmael, 1835

Subgenus: *Allotypus* Förster, 1862

**Opius (Allotypus) arenaceus* Jakimavicius, 1986

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Girne, Çatalköy, wild herb, 08.04.2015, 1♀.

Hosts: Unknown.

Distribution: Western Palaearctic, Cyprus (**New record**).

Subgenus: *Gastrosema* Fischer, 1972

**Opius (Gastrosema) caucasi* Tobias, 1986

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Beşparmak, Taşocağı, wheat, 08.04.2015, 1♀; İskele, 07.04.2015, wheat, 1♀.

Host: Diptera, **Agomyzidae:** *Phytomyza horticola* Goureau, 1851.

Distribution: Palaearctic, Cyprus (**New record**).

Subgenus: *Nosopoea* Förster, 1862

**Opius (Nosopoea) sigmodus* Papp, 1981

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Girne tepebaşı, wild herb, 09.04.2015, 1♀.

Hosts: Unknown.

Distribution: Western Palaearctic.

****Opius (Nosopoea) speciosus* Fischer, 1959**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Lefkoşa, Devlet üretim çiftliği, wild herb, 09.04.2015, 1♂.

Hosts: Unknown.

Distribution: Western Palaearctic, Cyprus (New record).

Subgenus: *Pendopius* Fischer, 1972

****Opius (Pendopius) bajariae* Fischer, 1989**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus Türkmenköy, wild herb, 09.04.2015, 1♂.

Hosts: Unknown.

Distribution: Western Palaearctic, Cyprus (New record).

Subfamily: Rogadinae

Genus: *Aleiodes* Wesmael, 1838

Subgenus: *Aleiodes* Wesmael, 1838

****Aleiodes (Aleiodes) bicolor* (Spinola, 1808)**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Köprüküy, wheat, 30.05.2016, 1♀.

Hosts: Unknown.

Distribution: Palaearctic, Cyprus (New record).

Subgenus: *Chelonorhogas* Enderlein, 1912

****Aleiodes (Chelonorhogas) eurinus* (Telenga, 1941)**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - İskele, wild herb, 07.04.2015, 1♂.

Hosts: LEPIDOPTERA, Noctuidae: *Apamea anceps* (Denis & Schiffermüller, 1775); *E. ochrogaster* (Guenée, 1852).

Distribution: Oriental, Palaearctic, Cyprus (New record).

Subgenus: *Neorhogas* Szépligeti, 1906

***Aleiodes (Neorhogas) ductor* (Thunberg, 1822)**

Material examined: Northern Cyprus - Beşparmak dağları, taşocağı, wild herb,

09.04.2015, 1♀, 4♂♂; Köprüküy, wheat, 30.05.2016, 1♀.

Hosts: LEPIDOPTERA, Lasiocampidae:

Euthrix potatoria (Linnaeus, 1758); *Anarta (Calocestra) trifolii* (Hufnagel 1766); *Autographa gamma* (Linnaeus, 1758); *Mamestra brassicae* (Linnaeus 1758);

Nymphalidae: *Brenthis ino* (Rottemburg 1775); **Sesiidae:** *Synanthedon scoliaeformis* (Borkhausen 1789).

Distribution: Palaearctic, Cyprus (Papp, 1998).

Discussion

The study was conducted in 108 localities covering the north of Cyprus. A total of 42 species belonging to 14 genera of Agathidae, Braconinae, Cheloninae, Doryctinae, Euphorinae, Homolobinae, Opiinae and Rogadinae are reported from Northern Cyprus. Twenty-six species are recorded from Cyprus for the first time. The hosts of 15 species are known.

Due to its geographical location, Braconidae species of Cyprus are very common (Table. 1). Distribution of Braconid species depends to the host species. 84% of Cyprus fauna restricted to the Western Palaearctic, 9% in both Palaearctic and Oriental, 4% Holarctic, 2.4% Nearctic, Neotropical, Oriental and Palaearctic. A small number of species have been recorded from a large number of zoogeographic regions. The most common species in the zoogeographic regions was *Homolobus (Apatia) truncator*. It has been recorded from Afrotropical, Holarctic, Neotropical and Oriental region and has about 55 host species. While *Glyptomorpha (Glyptomorpha) pectoralis* and *Bracon (Rostrobracon) urinator* are recorded from Afrotropical, Oriental and Palaearctic regions. It was the most common species of north Cyprus with 12 locality records. The other most common species is *Meteorus rubens*. It has been recorded from Holarctic, Neotropical and Oriental regions.

Table 1. Distribution of species from Cyprus based on biogeographic regions.

Zoogeographical regions	Number of species
Afrotropical, Australasian, Oceanic, Oriental, Eastern Palaearctic.	1
Afrotropical, Australasian, Oriental, Holarctic.	1
Afrotropical, Australasian, Nearctic, Neotropical Oceanic, Oriental, Palaearctic.	1
Afrotropical, Oceanic, Western Palaearctic.	1
Afrotropical, Oceanic, Oriental, Palaearctic.	1
Afrotropical, Nearctic, Neotropical, Oceanic, Oriental, Palaearctic.	1
Afrotropical, Nearctic, Neotropical, Oriental, Palaearctic.	1
Afrotropical, Nearctic, Neotropical, Palaearctic.	1
Afrotropical, Oriental, Palaearctic.	2
Afrotropical, Palaearctic.	2
Afrotropical, Holarctic, Oceanic.	1
Australasian, Nearctic, Neotropical, Oceanic, Oriental, Palaearctic.	1
Australasian, Oceanic, Oriental, Palaearctic.	1
Australasian, Nearctic, Neotropical, Oceanic, Palaearctic.	1
Holarctic.	5
Holarctic, Oriental and introduced into USA (Oregon).	1
Nearctic, Eastern Palaearctic.	1
Nearctic, Neotropical, Oceanic, Oriental, Palaearctic.	1
Nearctic, Neotropical, Oceanic, Palaearctic.	1
Nearctic, Neotropical, Oriental, Palaearctic.	3
Neotropical, Western Palaearctic.	1
Oceanic, Palaearctic.	1
Oriental, Palaearctic.	11
Palaearctic.	64
Western Palaearctic.	19
Total	124

The geographical land nearest to Cyprus is Anatolia. The braconidae fauna of Cyprus is similar to the braconidae fauna of Anatolia in accordance with the island biogeography theory (Aydođdu & Beyarslan, 2002, 2006a, 2006b, 2006c, 2009; Beyarslan, 1996, 2011, 2014, 2015a, 2015b, 2015c, 2016; Beyarslan & Aydogdu, 2012, 2013; Beyarslan & Çetin Erdoğan, 2011; Beyarslan & Fischer 2013; Beyarslan et al., 2013; Çetin Erdoğan & Beyarslan, 2016; Çetin Erdoğan et al., 2009, Fischer & Beyarslan, 2011, 2012, 2013).

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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مطالعه تاکسونومیک فون زنبورهای خانواده Braconidae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonoidea) در شمال قبرس

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چکیده: به منظور شناسایی فون زنبورهای براکونیده، نمونه‌های حشرات کامل این زنبورها از زیستگاه‌های مختلف در شمال قبرس بین سال‌های ۲۰۱۲ تا ۲۰۱۶ جمع‌آوری شد. نمونه‌برداری در هر دو گروه زیستگاه‌های طبیعی و مناطق کشاورزی با استفاده از روش تورجارو انجام شد. به طور کلی ۴۲ گونه متعلق به ۴ جنس از زیرخانواده‌های Agathidinae, Braconinae, Cheloninae, Doryctinae, Euphorinae, Homolobinae, Opiinae و Rogadinae از این منطقه گزارش شدند که از بین آنها ۲۶ گونه برای اولین بار گزارش می‌شوند.

واژگان کلیدی: کوه پنج‌دندانه، براکونیده، مجموعه جانوری، قبرس، پارازیتوئید